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NIGERIAN PENSION REFORMS AND MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study examines Nigerian pension reforms and management. It employed the library research approach which formed the basis for drawing up conclusion by the Researcher.

It was discovered from extant literature that despite the series of reforms in the Nigerian Pension system, Pension administration and management has been largely weak, inefficient and cumbersome due to poor staffing and equipping. This has more often than not led to poor record keeping in pension offices through the country as a result of which many pensioners had to spend years before their retirement benefits were paid.

This study posits that in an effort to achieve an effective pension reforms vis-à-vis pension system in Nigeria, the under listed recommendations are significant: the pension system should be adequately funded; computerized documentation and record keeping in all pension offices should be adopted; competent and experienced staff should be employed to handle pension activities across the nation; those who contravene any section of the Act should be punished by the law as stipulated in the Act with fear of favour; and the institutions that are charged with pension administration should be strengthened by quality legislature to stream line the documentations, prompt and ease of payment to pension beneficiaries.

Keywords: Pension reforms, Pension administration, Pension management.

1.0 Introduction

Pension as a form of social security against old-age poverty . Pension programmes, are generating the need for reforms. Pension reform is an act of adjusting the present pension system by making it more cost-effective, target-efficient and cost-beneficial for the beneficiaries (Kareem & Kareem, 2009). In an attempt to appropriately manage pension funds, several pension systems have been advanced. MacGreenvey (1990), made a distinction between Pay As You Go (PAYG), Fully Funded (FF) and Notional Defined Contribution

Accounts. However, a broader perspective was brought to this classification by Lindbeck and Persson (2003).

These reforms gave birth to the idea of pension fund and as a result administrators were introduced to manage the pension contributions of the employees (Mamud, 2014). The first legislative document on pension in Nigeria that was the 1951 Pension Ordinance . While it was retroactive effect from January 1, 1946. And since then there has been several pension reforms in the country with the two latest being the Pension Reform Act of 2004 and 2014. Due to the yearnings of the people for an improved pension system in Nigeria, the Pension reforms act of 2004 was enacted. However, this act was not left without flaws, thus, giving rise to the recently promulgated Pension Reform Act of 2014 which was signed in to Law by the erstwhile President-Goodluck Jonathan on 1st July, 2014.

Ndaghu (2015) asserts that Pension administration and management has been largely weak, in efficient and cumbersome due to poor staffing and equipping. According to Okotoni and Akeredolu (2005), the management of pension scheme in Nigeria is inundated by multiple and diverse problems. It is against this backdrop that this study tends to examine pension reforms and its management in Nigeria.

The remaining part of this paper is sectioned as follows: Section two considers a review of literature on the subject matter, section three discusses the theoretical framework, and lastly, section four summarizes and concluded the paper with some recommendations advanced.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Pension

According to Adams (2005) the pension is an amount paid by the government or by the company to its employee after working for some specific period of time, It is equally seen as the monthly amount that is paid to a retired officer till the time he dies because that officer had been working with the organization paying the sum. Ozor (2006) opines that Pension consists of lump sum payment paid to an employee upon his disengagement from active service. pension plans may be contributory or noncontributory; group or individual; insured or trustee , fixed or variable benefits; private or public, and single or multi-employer. A pension plan which is generally created by the employer considering the benefit of employees

. It is commonly referred to as an occupational or employer pension (Ayegba, James, & Odoh, 2013). Pension has also been defined as a fixed periodic income or annuity payment that is made at or after retirement to employee who has become eligible for benefits through age, earnings and service (Eme, & Sam, 2011). Odia and Okoye (2012) stated in their work “Pension Reform in Nigeria, is considered too old or have reached the statutory age for retirement. According to Eme, Uche and Uche (2014), pension is referred to a fixed amount that is to be paid at regular interval to a person. It is typically following retirement from service either based on ill health, having reached the retirement age or decided to disengage from service before his/her retirement date.

2.2 Concept of Pension Reforms

Pension reform is an act of adjusting the present pension system by making it more cost-effective, target-efficient and cost-beneficial for the beneficiaries (Kareem & Kareem, 2009). Thus, the aim of any reform is to correct the imbalances and distortion According to Abromovits (2003) in an article; “Contributory pension scheme: In the case of Brazil “A pension system is considered essentially as an income security program which provides benefit to the beneficiaries who are supposed to be retired persons, or pensioners or the poor. These benefits can be defined or flat. Different classifications was given to pension systems, however, in the pension literature; pension systems might be between defined benefit and defined contribution (DC) systems. Kotikoff (1996) takes pension systems to be between Pay-As-You-Go (PAYG) and DC are fully funded (FF) pension programmes. The distinction that was made between FF, PAYG, and Notional Defined Contribution Accounts by MacGreenvey (1990). However, a broader perspective was brought to this classification by Lindbeck and Persson (2003).

2.3 History of the Nigerian Pension Reforms

The pension legislative document in Nigeria was the 1951 Pension Ordinance which has retroactive effect from January 1, 1946. The Ordinance provided public servants with both pension and gratuity (Ahmad, 2006). However, the first private sector pension scheme in Nigeria set up for the employees of the Nigerian Breweries was in 1954.

Due to the yearnings of the people for an improved pension system in Nigeria, the Pension reforms act of 2004 was enacted. However, this act was not left without flaws, thus, giving

rise to the recently promulgated Pension Reform Act of 2014 which was signed in to Law by the erstwhile President-Goodluck Jonathan on 1st July, 2014.

2.4 Nigerian Pension Reform Act 2004

On June 11, 2004, the then President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo signed the Pension Reform Act 2004 into Law. In both its objectives and features, the Act marks a turning point in Nigeria's annals of pension regimes. Some of the provisions and features of the scheme include: i) It is a contributory pension scheme, ii) The scheme applies to all employees, iii) It makes it compulsory for every person in employment in Nigeria so that he can save towards catering for their livelihood during old age; iv) Provides for a uniform set of rules, regulations , standards and for the administration and for the payment of retirement benefits v) Stipulates 50 years as the age at which an employee is entitled to pension; vi) Mandates all employers have to maintain life insurance policy in the favour and welfare of the employee for a minimum of three times than annual total emolument of the employee; vii) Allows for increase in the rates of monthly contributions, subject to agreement between the employer and the employee; viii) Directs every employee to maintain Retirement Savings Account (RSA) in his name with any Pension Fund Administrator (PFA) of his choice; ix) Makes pension deductions transferable from one employer to another .

2.5 The Ambiguities in Pension Reform Act 2004 Provisions

Although, one would have said the various provisions of the scheme as highlighted above would bring succor in the later year for the retirees, though, the various challenges have hampered the success of the scheme and its attempt at achieving its fundamental objectives. These ambiguities according to Olanrewaju (2011) include:

2.6 Nigerian Pension Reform Act 2014

According to Onyenkpa (2014), the newly enacted Pension Reform Act, 2014 provides for the following (in summary):

A higher threshold number of employees for participation under the new pension plan system: The minimum threshold that is for private sector employers is that they have to participate in the Scheme as it is now 15 (previously 5) employees.

The salient features of the New Pension Reform Act 2014 according to Pwc (2014) include:

2.7 Appraisal of the Nigerian Pension Reform Act 2014

Ensuring greater protection of pension fund assets has been the core mandate for the National Pension Commission (PenCom) since its formation following the Pension Reform Act (PRA) 2004. PenCom is the body tasked with regulating, supervising and ensuring effective administration of pension matters in Nigeria. Prior to the enactment of the PRA 2004 and the subsequent formation of PenCom,. These issues have since been resolved following the introduction of the Defined Benefit Contributory Pension Scheme. Under this system, the employees contribute a minimum amount of their basic salary, housing and transport allowances. Equally; employers are obliged to contribute a pre-agreed amount on behalf of their employees.

The New Pension Act expanded the coverage of the Defined Contributory Pension Scheme in the private sector . Furthermore the new Act increased the minimum rate of pension contribution from 15 percent of monthly employment, while 8 percent will be contributed by employees and 10 percent by the employers. Thereby enhance their monthly pension benefits and retirement.

The 2014 Act also empowers PenCom subject to the fiat of the Attorney General of the Federation, to institute criminal proceedings against employers who persistently fail to deduct and / or remit pension contributions specially with in the stipulated time. This was not provided for by the 2004 Act.

With the new law in place, it is obvious that the National pension commission has not only been given enough room to improve its activities but also employers to ensure that employers who fail to remit deductions are penalized and the amount owed duly paid. Prior to the new law, the commission reported that it had recovered a total of N13.33 billion from employers who defaulted in remitting pension deductions from their employees under the new Contributory Pension Scheme (CPS). The amount includes interests calculated along with the principal sum (Jonathan, 2014).

2.8 Pension Scheme Management in Nigeria

A pension scheme according to Kareem and Kareem (2009) is usually a regular payment made by the government or private companies or organizations to their retirees as a form of

social security against old-age risks and uncertainties. Pension programmes are also used to promote a ‘saving culture’ among current employees, and this stimulates savings. There are two types of pension scheme: private and public.

Ndaghu (2015) asserts that Pension administration and management has been largely weak, in efficient and cumbersome due to poor staffing and equipping. This has more often in comparison to not led to poor record keeping all pension offices through the country as a result of which .many pensioners had to spend years before their retirement benefits were paid.

According to Okotoni and Akeredolu (2005), the management of pension scheme in Nigeria is inundated by multiple and diverse problems. One key problem is the lack of adequate funding. Another dimension of the problem is the phenomenon whereby pension funds are released directly to underwriters. This scenario has further complicated the problem, resulting in accumulated arrears of pensioners.

The continuous petitions and appeals for recalculations and computations of gratuity and pension from pensioners is another problem. Many pensioners are dissatisfied with the calculations of their entitlements which they allege are wrongly computed.

There is also the problem of the strategic method of downsizing and rationalization of personnel so that they can reduce the labour costs , operating costs, and promote efficiency. The main paradox here is that the costs of paying retirement and pension benefits are higher than the costs of retaining them.

3.0 Theoretical Framework

3.1 The Lifecycle Hypothesis:

This hypothesis has set the standard for analyzing expenditure decision in relation to pensions. pension basic structure and the forces and influences that motivate savings by individuals. This hypothesis was associated with Modigliani and Brumberg (1954) and Ando and Modigliani (1963). The theory posited that consumption is a kind of function of lifetime wealth as well as it does not affected by changes in the pattern of income over time,

4.0 Summary, Conclusion and Recommendation

4.1 Summary and Conclusion

Pension as earlier stated refers to a fixed sum to be paid regularly to a person, typically following retirement from service either based on ill health, having reached the retirement age or decided to disengage from service before his/her retirement date. There are four main classifications of pensions in Nigeria: retiring pension, compensatory pension, superannuating pension, and compassionate allowance. The first legislative document on pension in Nigeria was the 1951 Pension Ordinance which has retroactive effect from January 1, 1946. And due to the yearnings of the people for an improved pension system in Nigeria, there has over the years been series of reforms. However, the current reform is the Pension Reform Act of 2014 which was signed into Law by the erstwhile President-Goodluck Jonathan on 1st July, 2014. Despite the series of reforms in the Nigerian Pension system, Pension administration and management has been largely weak, inefficient and cumbersome due to poor staffing and equipping. This has more often than not led to poor record keeping in pension offices through the country . It has resulted as many pensioners are supposed to spend years before their retirement benefits are paid. Other problems with the management of pension scheme in Nigeria include: lack of adequate funding, accumulated arrears of pensioners, incompetent and inexperienced pension staff, series of litigation issues, etc.

4.2 Recommendations

In an effort to achieve an effective pension reforms vis-à-vis pension system in Nigeria, the under listed recommendations are significant:

- i. The pension system should be adequately funded.
- ii. Computerized documentation and record keeping in all pension offices should be adopted.
- iii. Competent and experienced staff should be employed to handle pension activities across the nation.
- iv. Those who contravene any section of the Act should be punished by the law as stipulated in the Act with fear of favour.
- v. The institutions that are charged with pension administration should be strengthened by quality legislature to stream line the documentations, prompt and ease of payment to pension beneficiaries.

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